

Temperature Predictions in Thick Composite Laminates at Low Cure Temperatures

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ABSTRACT

This paper contains results from experiments and simulation of the cure behaviour of thick glass/epoxy composite laminates cured at low initial temperatures. The objective is to study how sensitive the temperature development in a commercial epoxy is to initial cure temperature for a few different combinations of wall thickness and fiber content. Measured results show the temperature development in thick composites with high fiber content to be sensitive to initial cure temperature. The accuracy of calculated temperatures is also discussed. For low initial cure temperatures, small inaccuracies in the reaction kinetics and material data will have a large effect on the predictions. These inaccuracies will furthermore affect the temperature predictions during the remaining cure cycle.

1 INTRODUCTION

Cure-heat transfer models have been verified for several cases, see for instance [1, 2]. Reaction kinetics data are however often measured at relatively high temperatures and matrix thermal properties are sometimes modelled as constants. Some resins are cured at low initial temperatures recommended by material supplier (60-70 °C below maximum T_g) and with a low reaction rate. This is the case in some components made by winding, RTM, casting, etc. The aim of this work is to study curing of a common epoxy under these conditions and calculated temperature accuracy. This is done by studying the sensitivity of the cure-heat transfer solution to fiber content and wall thickness. These two parameters control the main factors during curing of a laminate, see [3]. Fiber content affects specific heat, thermal conductivity, density and heat of reaction. The wall thickness strongly affects the cure-heat transfer behaviour.

2 MODELS

2.1 Energy equation

The energy equation for one-dimensional heat transfer of a cylinder with internal heat generation in the resin is written as

$$\rho C \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} = \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} (K_r r \frac{\partial T}{\partial r}) + \rho_r v_r \dot{Q}_r \quad (1)$$

where T is temperature, t is time, r is radial coordinate, ρ is density, K_r is thermal conductivity in the r direction and C is specific heat. K_r and C depends on both temperature and degree of cure for the composite. \dot{Q}_r is the rate at which heat is generated or absorbed by chemical reactions in the resin, ρ_r is the resin density and v_r is the volume fraction of resin in the composite. If a large radius is studied, $r \rightarrow \infty$, and the equation corresponds to the plane one-dimensional problem. The degree of cure α and the rate of heat generation is defined as

$$\alpha = \frac{Q_r}{H_u}, \quad \dot{Q}_r = \left(\frac{d\alpha}{dt} \right) H_u = (f(\alpha, T)) H_u \quad (2)$$

where Q_r is the heat evolved from time $t=0$ to time t , and H_u is the total heat of reaction of the resin. The rate of reaction da/dt is assumed to be described by a relation $f(\alpha, T)$ which is unique for every resin formulation. The current process model neglects the chemical reaction that might occur during the creation of the physical structure, i.e. winding stage for pipes and mold filling for plates, since this is assumed to occur at low temperature when the rate of reaction is very slow. The initial temperature T_{m0} in mandrel, T_{c0} in composite and the initial degree of cure α_0 at time t_0 when reaction starts are defined (3).

$$T = T_{m0} \quad T = T_{c0} \quad \alpha = \alpha_0 = 0 \quad \text{at } t = t_0 \quad (3)$$

$$-K_r \left. \frac{\partial T}{\partial r} \right|_{\text{wall}} = \kappa_i (T_{wi} - T_{\infty i}) \quad \text{at } r = R_{mi} \text{ for } t > t_0 \quad (4)$$

$$-K_r \left. \frac{\partial T}{\partial r} \right|_{\text{wall}} = \kappa_o (T_{wo} - T_{\infty o}) \quad \text{at } r = R_{mo} + h \text{ for } t > t_0 \quad (5)$$

The boundary conditions are defined with use of general temperature boundary conditions (4,5). κ_i is heat transfer coefficient, T_{wi} wall temperature and $T_{\infty i}$ ambient temperature at the inner surface of the mandrel. κ_o is heat transfer coefficient, T_{wo} wall temperature and $T_{\infty o}$ ambient temperature at the outer surface of the composite. R_{mi} and R_{mo} are the inner and outer radius of the mandrel, and h is the composite thickness of the cylinder.

2.2 Thermal properties

Matrix density ρ_m is approximated with a constant. Some matrix material parameters are known to vary significantly during cure [4-7]. A linear interpolation formula has been used to approximate dependence on temperature and cure for matrix specific heat c_m . The approximate formula [4, 5] by Mijovic has been used for the dependence of matrix thermal conductivity λ_m on temperature and cure. T is defined in $^{\circ}\text{C}$. A-G are curve fitting constants.

$$c_m = A + (B + C\alpha)T + D\alpha, \quad \lambda_m = E + (FT + G)\alpha \quad (6)$$

Fiber thermal properties are assumed to be constant. In this report $\lambda_f = 0.93 \text{ W/m}^{\circ}\text{C}$, $c_f = 840 \text{ J/kg}^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $\rho_f = 2540 \text{ kg/m}^3$ was used for glass fiber. Transverse thermal conductivity is calculated using formulas by Nielsen [8]

$$\frac{\lambda_c}{\lambda_m} = \frac{1 + ABv_f}{1 - B\Psi v_f}, \quad A = k_E - 1, \quad B = \frac{(\lambda_f/\lambda_m) - 1}{(\lambda_f/\lambda_m) + A}, \quad \Psi = 1 + \left(\frac{1 - v_{\max}}{v_{\max}^2} \right) v_f \quad (7)$$

where k_E is the generalized Einstein coefficient (1.84), v_{\max} is maximum fiber volume fraction (0.82), λ_f , λ_m and λ_c are the transverse thermal conductivities for fiber, matrix and composite and v_f is the fiber volume fraction. Density and specific heat are calculated from the exact definition where ρ_f , ρ_m and ρ_c are the densities for fiber, matrix and composite. c_f , c_m and c_c are the specific heat for fiber, matrix and composite and v_m is matrix volume fraction.

$$\rho_c = v_f \rho_f + v_m \rho_m, \quad c_c = (v_f c_f \rho_f + v_m c_m \rho_m) / \rho_c \quad (8)$$

2.3 Reaction kinetics

The cross linking reaction is an exothermal reaction promoted by heat. The thermal balance will therefore be very important for the advancement of reactions and the formed molecular structure. Gelation does not affect the curing reaction rate [9]. The glass transition temperature T_g is defined as the temperature where the liquid or gelled resin is transformed into a glass. This phenomenon, usually termed vitrification, can occur during cure and does affect the reaction rate considerably due to a shift from chemical to diffusion controlled reaction. A model for the rate function $f(\alpha, T)$ based on [10,1] have been proposed [11]

$$d\alpha / dt = (k_1 + k_2 \alpha^m)(\beta - \alpha)^n, \quad k_i = A_i \exp(-E_i / RT), \quad i=1,2 \quad (9)$$

where both k_1 and k_2 are temperature dependent rate constants expressed as an Arrhenius relation where A_i is a constant, E_i is the activation energy, R is the gas constant and T the absolute temperature. β is the final degree of reaction at an isothermal cure temperature. As the polymerization reaction advances, the glass transition temperature will increase up to the point where it reaches the cure temperature. The parameter β is a correction for a stop in reaction at the stage where the molecular mobility is strongly reduced, i.e. at T_g . β is a function of temperature and a linear form has been obtained [1]

$$\beta = p + q T, \quad \text{for } T < T_{gm} \quad \text{and } 0 \leq \beta \leq 1.0 \quad (10)$$

where p and q are constants and T_{gm} is the glass transition temperature for the fully cured system. Temperature compensation can be added to n using a polynomial with constants a and b .

$$n = a + b T, \quad \text{for } T < T_{gm} \quad (11)$$

2.4 Analysis

A computer program has been developed by modifying software kindly supplied by Stanford University [12] and used to simulate the curing process for one-dimensional heat transfer using large radius, $r \rightarrow \infty$, so that the equations (1-5) corresponds to the plane problem. The numerical solution is obtained with a finite difference method using an implicit alternating-direction method. Due to geometrical and boundary condition symmetry only half the plate need to be calculated, see Fig. 1. Both the plate and pipe can be considered as consolidated before curing so all flow effects are neglected in the analysis. The measured temperature in the aluminium plate was used in the calculations as boundary conditions. This was done in order to reduce the influence of transverse heat flow in the relatively small plate. The same software was used for the pipe. A constant value for the outer heat transfer coefficient was obtained by curve fitting on measured temperatures up to 50 °C, which gave a value around 30 W/m²°C. The heat transfer coefficient was varied in repeated calculations until the initial temperature in the composite agreed well with the corresponding measured temperature. The inner mandrel boundary is thermally insulated since the mandrel has closed ends and the heat capacity of air is very small. It can be noted that the composite plate thickness should be roughly two times thicker than the pipe thickness to give a similar thermal analysis problem. This is due to the use of thermal insulation boundary conditions and oven curing in both cases. The main difference is the placement of mandrel and composite relative to the boundary conditions.

Figure 1. Boundary conditions for thermal analysis of half the plate and the complete pipe.

3 EXPERIMENTAL

Used resin was CIBA anhydride epoxy LY556/HY917/DY070 with a mixing ratio of 100:90:0.5 by weight. This system can be characterized as a heat curing epoxy. The manufacturers recommended cure cycle is 4 h 80 °C + 8 h 140 °C. Specific heat for the epoxy was measured using a Perkin Elmer DSC7 apparatus. The apparatus was calibrated against standard specimens before the measurement. Comparative measurements on distilled water were made to check the measuring procedure. Several measurements were made on fully cured

and uncured epoxy. Accelerator was not added to the resin formulation for the uncured case to avoid chemical reaction during measurement. Thermal conductivity was estimated from temperature calculations and measurements on similar materials. The DSC7 was used to measure the data used for the reaction kinetics model. Separate measurements were made at 80 °C due to accuracy problems created by the low reactivity at this temperature. Degree of cure versus time was measured by isothermal curing at 80 °C in a DSC for a specified time. The remaining heat of reaction for the sample was measured using a dynamic DSC measurement. The viscosity as function of time during isothermal curing at 80 °C was measured using a Bohlin Visco 88BV and according to DIN 53019. The degree of cure when viscosity reaches 1000 mPas is used to define gelation.

A piece of wood was used to create a pure resin or composite thickness of 19 mm as measured on the cured plate and give thermal insulation. Tool width is 170x170 mm with 10 mm aluminium thickness. One temperature sensor was placed in the middle of the tool plate and two temperature sensors were placed in the middle of the composite. The previously mentioned epoxy was poured into the assembled tool at room temperature and then placed in a convection oven for heat treatment. The ambient temperature was kept constant in the oven. The duplicated temperature sensors in the middle of the composite gave consistent results. Wet filament winding was used to manufacture glass/epoxy pipes. Mandrels equipped with a temperature sensor on the inner surface have been used. Main dimensions were $t=5$ mm, $\varnothing=150$ mm and $L=900$ mm. A temperature sensor was placed in the middle of the composite wall thickness during winding. Epoxy temperature in the impregnation bath was 40 °C. The pipes were cured in a convection oven and the temperatures were recorded.

4 RESULTS

4.1 Epoxy thermal properties

Figure 2. Measurements and model for specific heat c_m .

The obtained parameters to (6) were $A = 1694.1$ J/kg°C, $B = 2.907$ J/kg°C², $C = 0.502$ J/kg°C², $D = -668.1$ J/kg°C, see Fig. 2. The measured variation of c_m with temperature and cure is significant. Estimations were used for the thermal conductivity. λ_m is 0.19 W/m°C for this fully cured epoxy at 23 °C according to data from the resin supplier and [13]. Initial λ_m for uncured epoxy at 20 °C was estimated to 0.14 W/m°C using curve fitting on temperatures below 50 °C in section 4.3. This agrees qualitatively with results in [4, 5]. The temperature dependence of cured epoxy was estimated from comparisons with data from a separate measurement. 1.5 mm thick laminates made from CIBA CY179/HY917/DY070 glass/epoxy and one pure vinylester were fabricated using RTM at SICOMP. They were sent to SINKU-RIKO, INC. in Yokohama for test measurements on their Laser Flash Thermal Constants analyzer. Data for CY179 were back calculated at SICOMP from the measured glass/epoxy laminate data using formulas in 2.2. The results are in Table 1 along with LY556/HY917/DY070. The values for the matrices all show significant variation with temperature. λ_m was taken as 0.24 W/m°C at 100 °C. The three mentioned values were used to obtain parameters to (6) resulting in $E = 0.14$ W/m°C, $F = 0.00065$ W/m°C² and $G = 0.035$ W/m°C, see Fig. 3. Density variation during cure for this epoxy is relatively small. A constant mean value $\rho_m = 1175$ kg/m³ was hence used.

Table 1. Measured fully cured matrix thermal properties.

Temp. (°C)	c _m CY179 (J/kg°C)	c _m Vinylester (J/kg°C)	c _m LY556 (J/kg°C)	λ _m CY179 (W/m°C)	λ _m Vinylester (W/m°C)	λ _m LY556 (W/m°C)
19	1200	1330	-	0.19	0.20	0.19
54	1690	1590	1210	0.24	0.22	-
104	2020	2230	1390	0.25	0.25	0.24 (Estimated)

Figure 3. Predicted thermal conductivity λ_m.

4.2 Reaction kinetics

Table 2. Reaction kinetics data.

H _U (J/g)	k ₁ (1/s)	A ₂ (1/s)	E ₂ (kJ/mol)	m (-)	a (-)	b (1/°K)	p (-)	q (1/°K)
368	0	1.24E7	74.68	0.30	-4.2589	0.013457	-1.1172	0.0051484

The degree of cure as function of time has been calculated from isothermal DSC tests in [11]. The total heat of reaction from the isothermal test at 140 °C has been used as the ultimate value H_U for the calculation of α. Values in Table 2 were obtained for (9-11) in the temperature range of 80-140 °C with m = 0.30. n was curve fitted to (11) and β to (10). k₂ agrees well with (9). Results for isothermal cure at 80, 100, 120 and 140 °C are plotted in Fig. 4. The agreement is good but the model predicts too low degree of cure for 80 °C. A more complex model would be needed to correct that without affecting the accuracy at higher temperatures. In a separate experiment, gelation was found to occur at 21 % degree of cure.

Figure 4. Isothermal cure. Lines represent the model predictions and dots are measured values.

4.3 Temperatures in plane epoxy laminates

A plate with pure epoxy (no filler) was cured in the convection oven at 70 °C, see Fig. 5. The exothermic peak temperature is only 74 °C. The accuracy of the predicted temperature is good.

A corresponding measurement was performed at 80 °C, see Fig. 6. The measured exothermic peak temperature is 94 °C due to a more rapid reaction behaviour. This epoxy is hence sensitive to the initial cure temperature. The calculated temperature in the middle of the epoxy at the exothermic peak is 91 °C with a slight shift in time. The deviation can probably be explained by small inaccuracies in epoxy material parameters and reaction kinetics model during cure.

Figure 5. Pure epoxy in plane tool at oven temperature 70 °C.

Figure 6. Pure epoxy in plane tool at oven temperature 80 °C.

4.4 Temperatures in plane composite laminate

A plate with epoxy and woven glass fiber was cured in the convection oven at 80 °C, see Fig. 7. The fiber content is 34 % by volume measured using weight analysis. The measured exothermic peak temperature is 87 °C, as compared with 94 °C in Fig. 6. The added glass fiber leads to a smaller epoxy content and increased thermal conductivity.

Figure 7. Epoxy and glass fiber in plane tool at oven temperature 80 °C.

4.5 Temperatures in 14.6 mm thick pipe

Table 3. Pipe data.

h (mm)	R _{mi} (mm)	R _{mo} (mm)	T _{m0} (°C)	T _{c0} (°C)	vf (-)	Mandrel material
14.6	70.1	74.9	22	22	0.64	Aluminium
50.4	71.0	75.0	26	32	0.59	Steel

A 14.6 mm thick pipe was made with data according to Table 3, see Fig. 8. The measured and calculated temperature difference between the mandrel and composite are less than 1 °C throughout the process and hence only temperatures in the composite are presented. A low mandrel and composite temperature can be observed during the winding stage due to the low epoxy impregnation temperature of 40 °C and the use of room temperature glass fibers and mandrel. The exothermic peak temperature of 86 °C indicate that this is a suitable initial oven temperature for this case. A study of predicted temperatures shows that the reaction stops at the end of the 80 °C oven stage. The calculated temperature increase to 140 °C is faster than measured. The general accuracy of the predicted temperatures are satisfactory.

Figure 8. Winding and curing of 14.6 mm thick pipe.

4.6 Temperatures in 50.4 mm thick pipe

Figure 9. Curing of 50.4 mm thick pipe.

A 50.4 mm thick pipe was made with data according to Table 3, see Fig. 9. Only the temperature in the composite is presented to make the plot clearer. The measured exothermic

peak temperature is 111 °C. The reactivity is negligible for some 8-9 hours and hence the temperatures decrease to 82 °C. Temperature behaviour up to 140 °C is smooth because the reaction is not restarted until the composite temperature passes 111 °C and the remaining heat of reaction in the experiment is low. The true reaction at 80 °C in the oven is faster than calculated. This conforms to the reaction kinetics behavior in section 4.2. The main deviation is created when the composite material temperature passes 50 °C. The likely explanation is inaccuracies in the reaction kinetics model at low temperatures.

5 CONCLUSIONS

Measured results indicate that the recommended initial cure temperature of 80 °C is too high with this epoxy for some combinations of fiber content and wall thickness since a large exothermic peak temperature is created. Resin systems with high reaction rates at low initial cure temperatures, as in this case, can be expected to offer particular difficulties for cure-heat transfer modelling. Direct measurements of matrix heat capacity, thermal conductivity and cure kinetics at low temperatures and low degree of cure are needed to obtain accurate temperature predictions. In this work was the matrix heat capacity directly measured while matrix thermal conductivity was obtained from curve fitting on temperature measurements and comparisons with measurements on a similar epoxy. The data was incorporated in a model to describe these parameters dependence on degree of cure and temperature. Accurate matrix thermal properties can be expected to be particularly needed when curing of laminates with low fiber content is studied, as in the tested plates. Material thermal properties are more constant for a case with high fiber content. The analysis of the 50.4 mm thick pipe with high fiber content indicate that the main calculation error is created from relatively small inaccuracies in reaction kinetics data/model at low temperatures (50-80 °C).

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